

LASER-ASSISTED THERMOPLASTIC TAPE PLACEMENT: EFFECTS OF THERMAL HISTORY AND PLACEMENT SPEED ON WEDGE PEEL STRENGTH OF CF/PA6

Victoria Zinnecker^{1*}, Chris. M. Stokes-Griffin¹, Paul Compston¹

¹ARC Training Centre for Automated Manufacture of Advanced Composites, Research School of Engineering, Australian National University, Canberra, ACT 2600, Australia

* Corresponding author (victoria.zinnecker@anu.edu.au)

Keywords: automated fibre placement, thermoplastic composite, wedge peel strength, laser

ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the effect of tape placement speed and process temperature on the wedge peel strength of unidirectional CF/PA6 laminates manufactured in a laser-assisted tape placement process. Placement trials were performed at three different speeds, 100 mm/s, 200 mm/s and 400 mm/s, with varying process temperatures between 250 °C and 400 °C. The process temperature was increased steadily by 30 °C increments in this range. The wedge peel strength was determined with a wedge with a thickness of 3.2 mm, a wedge angle of 30° and a displacement rate of 1 mm/s. The maximum wedge peel strength (6.99 N/mm) was obtained at a tape placement rate of 100 mm/s and tape temperature set point of 340 °C. At increasing processing speeds the impact of the nip point temperatures reduces. Thus, the scatter of the wedge peel strength values is reduced by 60.8% for doubling the speed and by 67.1% for quadrupling the speed. The effect of the applied polyimide film for the wedge peel testing was found to reduce the process temperature for the third ply. Also, higher process speeds lead to a more evenly distributed temperature history without overshooting in temperature and therefore overheating the incoming tape.

1 INTRODUCTION

Automated manufacturing technologies are of interest to industry sectors such as automotive that are using lightweight composites due to the potential for reduced labour costs and increased productivity. Automated fibre or tape placement (AFP/ATP) of composites is one of the most advanced processes to build high performance continuously reinforced composite parts. It is already well established for thermoset composites; however thermoplastic-based composites can enable high-rate in situ consolidation and potential for end-of-life recyclability. ATP of thermoplastic composites with in situ consolidation is possible with high power near-infrared (NIR) diode laser, which is used to melt the surface of the substrate and the incoming tape during the tape placement process. However, this process still needs to be optimized as the thermal history of the process can have a significant influence on laminate quality and performance. Processing with insufficient heat will lead to no or poor bonding between the plies, overheating will lead to degradation of the polymer. Reducing the manufacturing time with increasing processing speed and obtained high performance properties, however, is a major cost saving factor. To understand the dependency between the temperature history and the processing speed for a CF/PA6 composite manufactured by a laser-assisted ATP process, the laminate quality will be evaluated by wedge peel tests. Samples will be produced with different temperatures and tape placement speeds and the obtained strength analysed.

2 MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

2.1 Material

Samples were manufactured with a fully impregnated 0.13 mm x 12 mm 48% v/v CF/PA6 unidirectional prepreg tape (*Celstran*® *CFR-TP PA6 CF60-01*, *Celanese Corporation, Irving, Texas, USA*). The typical melting point of the PA6 matrix is 220 °C. For separating the samples between ply two and three to introduce the wedge for the wedge peel testing, a polyimide film was used.

2.2 Laser-assisted ATP system

Laser-assisted automated tape placement belongs to the group of additive manufacturing processes in which parts are produced by adding one layer of composite to a previous one. Generally, a robot guided placement head lays up tapes of thermoset or thermoplastic composite sequentially onto a mould or a winding mandrel. The thermoset layup needs to get compacted and cured in an autoclave, whereas the thermoplastic variant can use a mobile heat source and a consolidation roller to start the in-situ process immediately while tape placing. Former ATP heads used a hot torch for this purpose, more modern heads are equipped with a multi kilowatt near infra-red (NIR) diode laser. For the ATP process a thermoplastic tape placement system from AFPT GmbH was used. The system's parameters are summarized in Table 1.

Parameter	Value	Unit
Laser Optics	16 x 44	mm
Placement Head Angle	30	°
Consolidation Roller Diameter	82	mm
Consolidation Roller Material	Silicone	-
Consolidation Roller Force	194	N

Table 1: Tape placement system parameters

The process temperature is controlled based on the apparent temperature of the observable surfaces of the substrate and the tape prior to the nip point. These contactless measurements are performed by a Long Wavelength Infrared (LWIR) sensor array. Deviations of the temperatures due to, for example, a change of the substrate surface texture (CF/PA6 tape vs. CF/PA6 tape with polyimide film), are controlled with a closed loop control that readjusts the laser power accordingly. The size of the focal spot causes an inertia, therefore spontaneous changes cannot be compensated immediately. The thermal camera monitoring the process control temperature is calibrated to a black-body source and the emissivity during pure tape placement is assumed to be unity ($\epsilon = 1.0$).

2.3 Specimen preparation

Four parallel CF/PA6 tape strips were placed on an Aluminium plate separated by a distance of 15 mm. The total length of each strip is 800 mm and each strip consists of 4 plies. A polyimide film was placed on top of the second ply of each strip to generate an un-bonded area for placing the wedge while testing. For the wedge peel tests, material symmetrical to the midline with a length of 260 mm respectively was used (see Figure 1 (a)). The ATP process control temperature was increased in 30 °C steps starting at 250 °C, ending with 400 °C. Each temperature was processed for 100 mm/s, 200 mm/s and 400 mm/s respectively. The sample manufacturing can be seen in Figure 1 (b).

Figure 1: Sample preparation (a) diagram, (b) experiment

2.4 Interlaminar strength characterization

The quality of the interlaminar bond is critical for the performance of the laminate whereas TP-ATP is known as a rapid interlaminar bond development process. For interlaminar strength characterisation wedge peel tests were performed as they have been commonly used as a quality indicator in TP-ATP studies [1–4].

Wedge peel tests are performed with a wedge with a thickness of 3.2 mm and a wedge angle of 30° as shown by [1]. The wedge is pulled through the mid-plane of the sample with a rate of 1 mm/s (see Figure 2).

Figure 2: Wedge peel testing (a) front view, (b) side view

The force is measured by a 1 kN load cell and the crossbeam displacement is logged at a rate of 50 Hz by the universal testing machine. For the analysis of the wedge peel strength the peel force of each specimen is used after stabilization over a length of 80 mm. The width of each specimen is measured 6 times along the specimen length and the mean value used for the calculation of the normalized wedge peel force per width. Typical force-displacement logs for different tape placement speeds at the same processing temperature at 340°C are shown in Figure 3 and Figure 4.

Figure 3: Typical force displacement graphs for the wedge peel tests showing the region of statistical evaluation for process temperature of 340 °C with (left) 100 mm/s (right) 200 mm/s.

Figure 4: Typical force displacement graphs for the wedge peel tests showing the region of statistical evaluation for process temperature of 340 °C with 400 mm/s.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the wedge peel tests are illustrated in Figure 5. For reference, the sample width used for normalization of the wedge peel strength is additionally included in the graphs. For comparison, values for CF/PA6 samples manufactured by press consolidation at 250 °C (~2.40 N/mm) and 270 °C (~2.49 N/mm) are used [1]. All wedge peel strength values for all three tape placement speeds are comparable or even outperforming these reference values for 250 °C with 2.37 N/mm for 100 mm/s, 3.57 N/mm for 200 mm/s and 3.99 N/mm for 400 mm/s.

For the tape placement speed of 100 mm/s it can be seen that the wedge peel strength increases for rising process temperature reaching the overall highest wedge peel strength value at 340 °C (6.99 N/mm) and flattens to a similar strength plateau for 370 °C and 400 °C with 6.11 N/mm and 6.07 N/mm respectively. The high standard deviation of 3.30 N/mm for the wedge peel strength for 340 °C at 100 mm/s mirrors the difficulties during placing the specimen in regards of tape roll ups around the consolidation roller. This could imply the combination of temperature and tape placement

speed is not within the optimal process window for placing CF/PA6 tapes with a stable process, especially considering, that for faster process speeds and temperatures the standard deviation also increases (e.g. $v = 200 \text{ mm/s}$, $400 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $\sigma = 2.47 \text{ N/mm}$). Also, the specimen geometry might need to be optimized. Placing the first ply down can result in a waviness of the tape, which can also effect the steadiness of the process and the control loop.

The wedge peel strengths for faster processing speeds is more balanced with the minimum values reaching 3.57 N/mm and 3.99 N/mm , maximum values reaching 5.38 N/mm and 5.51 N/mm for 200 mm/s and 400 mm/s respectively, resulting in a difference of 1.81 N/mm for 200 mm/s and 1.52 N/mm for 400 mm/s over the processing temperature range. This data indicates a more constant process window with less stadard deviation on the wedge peel strength and therefore, less influence of the temperature between $250 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and $370 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for the processed composite, especially for a tape placement speed of 200 mm/s . Similiar behaviour can be seen for the processing speed of 400 mm/s , where in general higher standard deviations are observable.

During the tape placement trials no matrix squeeze out was observed. Therefore, the deviation of the width is within the scope of measurement accuracy.

Figure 5: Effect of process temperature and tape placement speed on wedge peel strength and specimen width.

Another explanation for high standard deviations could be the impact of the applied polyimide film on the thermal history of the third ply. The bonding between the second and third ply of the laminate is of particular interest, as the wedge is introduced here during testing. This impact on the control temperature of the third ply for each track is shown in Figure 6 for 340 °C at 100 mm/s and Figure 7 for 400 mm/s. The biggest difference for both speeds is the oscillation and overshooting of the process temperature at lower speeds, whereas at higher speeds, the impact of the polyimide film is less and the control unit is capable of adjusting the tape temperature to the actual temperature set point of 340 °C without overshooting. This behaviour is due to a delay in the control system which allows at high processing speeds to overcome a change in surface texture and laser absorptance coefficient faster. To avoid a change of the processed temperature in general, it might be necessary to place the layers with expected disturbance with fixed laser power.

Figure 6: Control temperature log for the third ply for each track at 340 °C with 100 mm/s

Figure 7: Control temperature log for the third ply for each track at 340 °C with 400 mm/s

To analyse the deviation of the processed temperature to the temperature set point of 340 °C, a statistical analysis was executed for stable process windows before (y position between 930 mm and 1030 mm) and after (y position between 1350 mm and 1450 mm) the section with applied polyimide film (see dashed lines in Figure 6). Figure 7 summarizes the temperature history, showing, that the effect of surface texture change is not as high for faster tape placement rates as it is for slower process speeds. Also the standard deviation for the process control temperature is almost 50% lower for higher speeds ($\sigma = 21.5$ °C for 100 mm/s, $\sigma = 11.4$ °C for 400 mm/s).

Figure 8: Statistical evaluation of the control temperature deviation from the temperature set point of 340 °C before and after the surface texture change for the third ply at 100 mm/s and 400 mm/s

4 CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

A laser-assisted tape placement process was used to manufacture unidirectional CF/PA6 laminates at three different speeds, 100 mm/s, 200 mm/s and 400 mm/s and with varying process temperatures of 30 °C increments starting at 250 °C and ending at 400 °C. The inter-laminar bond quality was assessed with a wedge peel test and the effect of the temperature history on the wedge peel strength was studied. The key findings are summarized below:

- The highest wedge peel strength of 6.99 N/mm was obtained at 340 °C with 100 mm/s.
- The highest standard deviation of the wedge peel strength of 3.30 N/mm was also found at 340 °C with 100 mm/s.
- The deviation of the wedge peel strength values can be reduced by doubling or quadrupling the tape placement speed by 60.8% and 67.1% respectively.
- All wedge peel strength values processed by laser-assisted tape placement (2.37 N/mm for 100 mm/s, 3.57 N/mm for 200 mm/s and 3.99 N/mm for 400 mm/s) are comparable or outperforming reported reference strengths of samples manufactured by press consolidation at 250 °C (~2.40 N/mm).
- The placement speed was found to have a statistically significant influence on the stability of the tape placement process.

Further work includes the comparison of the wedge peel strength with the compression shear strength of the samples. Wedge peel strength is known to be more sensitive to the degree of crystallinity of the polymer and therefore samples with high crystallinity might have a lower fracture toughness compared to a sample with a more amorphous structure. Also, the impact of the crystallinity level of different composites placed at different speeds and temperatures will be investigated with Differential Scanning Calorimetry (DSC) measurements.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This project was conducted within the ARC Training Centre for Automated Manufacture of Advanced Composites (IC160100040), supported by the Commonwealth of Australia under the Australian Research Council's Industrial Transformation Research Program. The support of AFPT GmbH for the provision experimental facilities and human resources is greatly acknowledged.

REFERENCES

- [1] P. Schäfer, "Consolidation of carbon fiber reinforced Polyamide 6 tapes using laser-assisted tape placement," Dissertation, Technische Universität München, München, 2017.
- [2] C. M. Stokes-Griffin, A. Kollmannsberger, P. Compston, and K. Drechsler, "The effect of processing temperature on wedge peel strength of CF/PA 6 laminates manufactured in a laser tape placement process," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **121**, 2019, pp. 84–91, (doi: [10.1016/j.compositesa.2019.02.011](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2019.02.011)).
- [3] M. A. Khan, P. Mitschang, and R. Schledjewski, "Identification of some optimal parameters to achieve higher laminate quality through tape placement process," *Advances in Polymer Technology*, **29**, 2010, pp. 98–111, (doi: [10.1002/adv.20177](https://doi.org/10.1002/adv.20177)).
- [4] A. J. Comer *et al.*, "Mechanical characterisation of carbon fibre-PEEK manufactured by laser-assisted automated-tape-placement and autoclave," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **69**, 2015, pp. 10–20, (doi: [10.1016/j.compositesa.2014.10.003](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compositesa.2014.10.003)).